

Quality of Work Life of Workers in Fireworks Industry – A Study

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OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 2

Month: March

Year: 2019

ISSN: 2321-4643

Impact Factor: 3.112

Citation:

Jegatheesan, K.
“Quality of Work Life of Workers in Fireworks Industry – A Study.”
Shanlax International Journal of Management,
vol. 6, no. S2, 2019,
pp. 29–34.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2591076>

Introduction

Quality of Work Life (QWL) activity picked up significance somewhere in the range of 1969 and 1974, when a general gathering of analysts, researchers, association pioneers and government staff created enthusiasm for how to enhance the nature of a person through hands on involvement. Nature of Work Life has been characterized by numerous scientists in an assortment of routes, for example, nature of work and business quality. QWL is extremely noteworthy with regards to pledge to work inspiration and occupation execution. It is how much individuals from a function association can fulfill imperative individual needs through their encounters in the association. Administrative desires are unequivocally connected with the authoritative nature of work life and it is an approach to encourage the satisfaction of human needs and objective accomplishment.

Many organizations i.e. from small to large scale have become a leading type of organization in the world. The present world is being ruled by these organizations which are directly involved in raising and controlling the nation's wealth and resources, economic, political, social, cultural etc.

Likewise fireworks are one of the labour intensive industries in the country. The fireworks industry plays a vital role in providing ample employment opportunities for the people in Tamilnadu. The industry produces crackers both for domestic consumption and export. The most of the units are small and medium in size. Which employs more than 70,000 people directly, apart from this more than 1,50,000 people are employed indirectly concerned with crackers manufacturing like paper tube making, wire cutting, box making, lorry transport, Sales and distribution all over the country. The growth of the fireworks industry stems from the adoption of latest technology and the effective utilization of the opportunities of its macro environment. The requiring raw materials are produced indigenously. A developing country like India offers millions of unemployed, with fireworks tasks as a gainful employment. The strong entrepreneurial plan and personalized skills of Tamilnadu contribute to the efficient management of negotiations and control of operations leading to the effectiveness, quick delivery and quality of products all over the world.

The fireworks business in Tamilnadu has risen as a chief provider of significant worth included things winning high remote trade. In the course of recent years, there has been an amazing change in innovation and extensive quantities of refined automated machines, undeniable handling units, and other hardware required in firecrackers industry have been transported in. Progressively over the yearly extra necessities of talented and untalented laborers are assessed to be in the range in the middle of 10,000 to 25,000 which demonstrates the interest of specialists. Then again the representatives of these enterprises feel that they are antagonistically influenced by impossible calendars, unreasonable wages, expanded working occasions, constrained extra minutes work, late landing of materials for generation, unpredictable reshuffling of work routines, clogged work places, low dimensions of self-sufficiency in their employments, absence of administrative mastery and arrangements to take care of their issues and so forth; which are on the whole firmly identified with the nature of their work life.

Materials and Methods

The Quality of Work Life in an organization is inevitable for the smooth running and success of its workers. It should be maintained effectively to ensure that all the workers are running at their peak potential and free from stress and strain. The Quality of Work Life can be affected due to many issues such as working conditions, workers health, improper social welfare measures, extended working hours, compulsory overtime, quality of life and the quality of work which are not yet addressed well etc increased stress level of the workers at their job and lead to job dissatisfaction in the study area.

As mentioned above one of the major problem faced by fireworks industry particularly attainment of quality of work life of workers in the study area. Because firework plays a crucial role in the promotion and development of economy and it is one of the explosive industries. The production of fireworks products is manual one, and labour is an important factor of production in the fireworks industry. Fireworks industries are mainly employing skilled, semi-skilled and unskilled workers; those who are neither educationally qualified nor technically experienced. Majority of the workers of these industries feels that their industry are not providing adequate measures to balance their work and personal life and thereby struggling to provide a congenial climate for the workers to attain the quality of work life.

In this context, it would be more relevant to make an attempt to study the problems related to Quality of Work Life which may help the industry to considerably reduce the attrition rate and to provide high level of job satisfaction to their workers. Therefore an attempt has been made to study the quality of work life of workers of fireworks industry in Tamilnadu.

On the basis of the foregoing research objectives, the following null hypotheses have been framed for the present study.

There is no relationship between gender, age, marital status, literacy level, educational qualification, family size of the workers, monthly income, religion of the respondents and level of quality of work life.

There is no significant difference in the level of quality of work life of workers on the basis of nature of job, designation of workers, type of appointment, working experience and age of entering the work.

The primary data were collected directly from the respondents through a well set pre-tested interview schedule in the study area. The secondary data were collected mainly from the books and publications of the inspector of factories, journals, magazines, and websites and so on.

In the study area workers are large in number and it is not feasible to collect the data from all the respondents. Therefore it is decided to apply sampling technique to study the current problem. The www.surveysystem.com is used to identify the sample size. According to this website, 390 is identified as appropriate sample size.

Results and Discussions

- The study discloses that majority of the respondents are female, (39.70%) of the respondents are under 26 – 35 years of age, (73.30%) of the respondents are married, (56.20%) of the respondents are literate.
- (39.27%) of the respondents have studied up to SSLC and an equal percentage have completed Higher Secondary Level.
- (73.60%) of the respondents live under nuclear family system in the study area.
- (44.60%) of the respondents have more than four members in their family.
- (44.10%) of the respondents have earned between Rs.5,001 to Rs.10,000 as monthly income.
- (83.10%) of the respondents are Hindus in the study area.
- (35.10%) of the respondents belong to BC category in the study area.
- (78.70%) of the respondents are non-administrative workers.
- (52.80%) of the respondents have worked as regular workers in their factory.
- To find out the factors influencing quality of work life of workers in fireworks industry, the factor analysis has been applied. The results of the factor analyses reveal that the factors are grouped under the following headings.
- Work Environment , Work Culture, Self Development, Freedom of Work, Compensation, Job Flexibility, Work Relationship
- The rotated factor matrixes for the variables relating to the factor which are the most influence in employee's quality of work life are given in table. Table 4.6 shows rotated component matrix.

Table 1 Rotated Component Matrix

S.No.	Statements	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
1	My supervisor is more trained person	.698	-.018	.102	.201	.170	.131	.020
2	I am clear what is expected from me at work	.671	.130	.151	.014	-.025	-.064	.350
3	My roles at work are very known to me	.638	.202	.134	.038	.094	-.225	.151
4	In general I am very happy	.576	.105	.205	.165	.156	.042	.050
5	My work /job is satisfactory, so that influences my positive morale on my job	.274	.631	.116	.124	.079	-.102	.026
6	I have great recognition in my factory. So that I have more satisfaction	.032	.617	-.054	.018	-.172	.057	.256

7	Management takes proper steps to maintain the privacy of the workers	.271	.572	.325	.030	.079	.026	-.162
8	I have enough privacy in my job	.225	.548	-.131	.097	.180	.229	-.193
9	I have not frustrated at all	-.101	.531	.158	.037	.151	.102	.203
10	I am able to do things as well as most people	.218	.104	.643	-.044	.010	-.007	.078
11	I get a sense of achievement from doing my job	-.032	.274	.597	.319	-.002	-.099	-.064
12	I enjoy with my work	.242	-.023	.566	.089	.102	.098	.151
13	Management is really interested in the welfare of workers	.453	-.015	.505	.172	.056	.159	.067
14	I feel able to voice opinions and influence changes in my area of work	.118	-.063	.130	.669	.039	.070	-.077
15	I am clear about the goals and objectives of my unit	.140	.159	.109	.625	-.037	.183	.014
16	My job is social in nature	.246	.231	-.137	.534	.136	-.019	.085
17	Job enlargement is more in factory	-.040	.162	.338	.501	.134	-.150	.342
18	My pay is enough to set necessary things in my life	.167	.004	.129	.003	.710	-.065	-.018
19	As per work requirement my pay is fair	.114	.073	.007	.208	.550	-.002	-.030
20	I have ample of opportunity to see the end results of my work	.055	.102	.174	.006	.519	.085	.288

21	My pay is the most important source for my job satisfaction from my job.	-.175	.335	.139	-.131	.518	.321	-.036
22	The organisation provides adequate facilities and flexibility for me to fit work in around in my family life	-.122	.130	-.121	.089	.123	.705	.073
23	I am happy to work with my manager/ supervisor/foreman	-.149	.007	.228	.267	.074	.672	-.147
24	Do you think that you get the wages you should have?	.273	.026	.058	-.078	-.042	.625	.174
25	There is no friction or anger between colleagues	.157	.054	.242	-.091	.186	.088	.508
	Percentage of variance	8.875	8.359	7.379	6.865	6.745	5.860	5.400
	Eigen value	2.929	2.758	2.435	2.265	2.226	1.934	1.782

Source: Computed Data

- The researcher has analyzed one way ANOVA to test the difference between employment details such as nature of job, designation of workers, working experience, type of appointment, age of entering the work and level of quality of work life. The outcome demonstrates that there is a critical difference between the variables.
- The researcher has applied to understand the level of satisfaction among the workers. In order to know the workers satisfaction, the researcher has administered factor analysis to analyse the factors influencing the opinion of workers towards Quality of Work Life. Based on the factor scores, the researcher has computed the level of Quality of Work Life. The level of workers satisfaction towards Quality of Work Life is measured into two levels such as satisfied and dissatisfied. The discriminant analysis reveals that the classification results over all 83.10 per cent of the cases correctly classified in the model. The value clearly shows the Unstandardized Canonical Discriminant Functions evaluated at group means 45.7 per cent of variance in the discriminating model between a prospective groups Satisfied / Dissatisfied is due to the changes in the seven predictor variables namely Work Environment, Work Culture, Self Development, Freedom of Work, Job Satisfaction, Relationship and Co-operation and Compensation.

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